

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF WOUNDED TYPE D.C. MOTOR WITH VARIABLE POWER SUPPLY

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Abstract:

In this paper we are observed about maximum R.P.M. , in this way we are used the Wounded type D.C. Motor with Variable Voltage Power Supply and 1Amp.,2Amp., 3Amp. For the purpose of the finding of the variable voltages we are used the voltages regulator. The Wounded type D.C. Motor are used in various industrial application.

Keywords: Word- Experimental Process; D.C. Power Supply; Wounded Type D.C. Motor.

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1. Introduction

Wounded type D.C. Motor are consisting with various parts such as armature, field winding, carbon bush and supporting structure. Armature is having the core, copper winding, slip ring. Armature is moving parts. The stator is stationary parts, which has metallic strip and winding.

2. Variable Voltage Power Supply

Figure 1: Power Supply

3. Wound Stators

Figure 2: Field coil are connected in shunt, in series, or in compound

Table 1: List of component

Sr. No.	component	specification
1	Wounded type Motor	D.C. power supply based
2	Connection Wire	2.5 mm
3	Power Supply	DC type
4	Load	D C type
5	Multimeter	Digital type
6	R.P. M. measurement device (Tachometer)	Digital Type

4. Performance Testing

4.1. Permanent Magnet Type D.C. Motor

12V D.C., 9V D.C., 6V. D.C. obtained by regulator
Current = 1 Amp.

Table 2: Voltage and R.P.M. using of Wounded type D.C. Motor

Sr. No.	Apply the Voltages in D.C.	R.P.M. measured by Tachometer
1	12	750
2	9	650
3	6	550

Figure 3: Voltage and R.P.M. using of Wounded type D.C. Motor

4.2. Permanent Magnet Type D.C. Motor

12V D.C., 9V D.C., 6V. D.C. obtained by regulator
Current = 2 Amp.

Table 3: Voltage and R.P.M. using of Wounded type D.C. Motor

Sr. No.	Apply the Voltages in D.C.	R.P.M. measured by Tachometer
1	12	1100
2	9	900
3	6	700

Figure 4: Voltage and R.P.M. using of Wounded type D.C. Motor

4.3. Permanent Magnet Type D.C. Motor

12V D.C., 9V D.C., 6V. D.C. obtained by regulator
Current = 3 Amp.

Table 4: Voltage and R.P.M. using of Wounded type D.C. Motor

Sr. No.	Apply the Voltages in D.C.	R.P.M. measured by Tachometer
1	12	1700
2	9	1500
3	6	1300

Figure 5: Voltage and R.P.M. using of Wounded type D.C. Motor

5. Conclusion

In this study we are achieving the maximum R.P.M. by Wounded type D.C. Motor. The maximum R.P.M. are 1700 R.P.M. and applied voltage are 12 Voltages D.C., which are shown in table.4, R.P.M. are measured by digital tachometer. The types of D.C, motor are very useful in industrial application.

References

- [1] A.S Larik, Syed Asif Ali Shah, Impacts on power factor of AC voltage controllers under nonsinusoidal condition, 3, April, 2012.
- [2] Chung.P, Proceeding of the IEEE International Conference on Electrical System, Singapore, pp-881-886, June, 2005.
- [3] Santosh S. A Comparison & Performance of Simulation Tools MATLAB/SIMULINK, 2, March 2012.
- [4] Imoru.O, Proceedings of the IEEE International Conferences on Machine design, China, pp 828-831, June 2012.
- [5] Ogata K., Modern Control Engineering, 5th ed., Prentice Hall, NJ, 2012.